

PARENTS' PERSPECTIVES ON NURSING SUPPORT IN PEDIATRIC WARDS: EVIDENCE FROM A SECONDARY-LEVEL HOSPITAL IN MIRPURKHAS, SINDH

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Abstract

Background: The hospitalization of a child is a highly stressful time for parents, often filled with fear and anxiety. Nurses are essential in providing emotional and informational support during this period. Parents' perceptions of nursing support are key indicators of care quality and satisfaction, yet there is a lack of evidence from secondary-level hospitals in developing regions. This study aimed to assess parents' perceptions of nursing care provided to children under the age of five years admitted to the pediatric department at District Headquarters Hospital Mirpurkhas in province of Sindh.

Methodology: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at the pediatric department of District Headquarters Hospital Mirpurkhas, from November 2025 to January 2026. A total of 130 parents of hospitalized children were selected using a non-probability convenience sampling technique. The data was collected using a structured, translated questionnaire based on the Nurse-Parent Support Tool (NPST). Data was analyzed using IBM SPSS version 27, utilizing descriptive statistical methods to sum up participants' attributes and perception scores.

Results: Most participants were female (76%). Approximately half of the parents (49%) were aged 25–35 years. Involving socioeconomic status, 64.6% of participants reported a monthly income of less than PKR 30,000. The overall mean score of the Nurse-Parent Support Tool (NPST) shown a good level of perceived nursing support ($\bar{X} = 3.79 \pm 0.40$). Emotional support domain of the NPST had the highest mean score ($\bar{X} = 4.15 \pm 0.89$), demonstrating compelling parental perception of nurses' emotional support.

Conclusion: This study determined that parents perceive nursing support in the pediatric department positively, with emotional care and responsiveness recognized as major strengths. These findings highlight the dire function of nurses in forming family experiences during pediatric hospitalization. Healthcare

institutions should prioritize family-centered nursing models, and structured nurse–parent communication. Incorporating these practices into institutional policies and pediatric care standards may lead to improved care experiences and outcomes for hospitalized children and their families.

INTRODUCTION

The hospitalization of a child is a profoundly stressful and emotionally challenging experience for parents, commonly accompanied by feelings of fear, anxiety, uncertainty, and a diminished sense of control (1). Hospitalization can be highly challenging for both children and their parents. Factors such as premature birth, admission to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU), and emergency or non-emergency pediatric admissions relate to a wide range of negative emotional responses among parents, such as, sadness, fear, hopelessness, anger, insecurity, depression, anxiety, and heightened parental stress (2). In pediatric departments, where both emergency and non-emergency admissions occur frequently, the involvement of family members is essential for providing support and disseminating information. However, many families report experiencing a lack of cognitive, emotional, and overall support from nursing staff (3). Providing supportive nursing care during a child's hospital stay reduces parents' stress and anxiety, makes it easier for them to transition into their new roles as parents, and promotes positive parent-child relationships. As a result, parental satisfaction is enhanced by the nurse's assistance (4). Nursing support for parents of inpatient children can improve the relationship between parents and children, lower parents' stress and anxiety levels, improve the parents' wellbeing, quality of life, and facilitate their transition to other parenting roles (5). Because parents of children in hospitals have more responsibilities due to their children's care needs, by helping parents is the cornerstone of nursing care. Nursing support for parents of inpatient children will improve the relationship between parents and children and lower parents' stress and anxiety levels, because it is a care philosophy that nurses incorporate into their professional practices without defining support as a distinct action(5).

Quality of care is crucial in modern healthcare, impacting patient satisfaction and competitiveness. Parents rely on their judgment about

their children's needs and seek reassurance from those providing the best care(6). However, recent literature highlights persistent gaps in nurse–parent interactions and supportive care practices. Studies have reported high levels of dissatisfaction with nursing support across different settings. In Amman, approximately 90% of parents reported that nurses omitted their children's demands because they didn't listen well and responded promptly (7). On the other hand, 49.2% of patients in Ethiopia were happy with nursing treatment, despite 51.67% of nurses exhibiting compassionate conduct (8). In India, 83% of parents expressed limited satisfaction with pediatric oncology treatment (9). According to Koirala Institute of Health Sciences, there was inadequate interaction between nurses and parents, and 59.9% of parents expressed dissatisfaction with the nursing treatment they received at Kanti Children's Hospital (10). In emergency community health services, communication and emotional support are frequently rated poorly, which is associated with unfavorable opinions of care (11). However, some studies particularly those conducted in neonatal intensive care units (NICUs), highlight the crucial role these units play in the care of critically ill newborns who require immediate medical attention after birth. Being a parent of a newborn in the NICU can be an incredibly stressful experience, especially when the nursing staff is unable to provide adequate support (12).

Parents' experiences in the PICU are distressing due to the abrupt nature of the admission, the unpredictable nature of the hospital stay and treatment, and the stressful surroundings (13). As a result, parents of critically sick children admitted to the PICU are vulnerable to long-term detrimental effects on their mental health, including sadness, anxiety, and posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD), following their discharge from the PICU and between 10% to 42% of parents suffer from PTSD, and

between 23% to 31% experience anxiety due to stressful past in the hospital (14).

Globally, the largest under-5 mortality occurs in developing countries, about 5 million children under the age of 5 died each year, mostly from causes that could be prevented or treated. Nearly half of these deaths, or 2.4 million, among newborns within their first 28 days of life (15, 16). The probability of a child dying between birth and age five per 1000 live births is known as the child mortality rate (CMR), and causes of CMR are varies, however, malaria, pneumonia, diarrhea, and other infectious disorders continue to be a major global cause of child mortality(17). Reducing mortality is partially dependent on each healthcare system's capacity to provide high-quality care at the patient satisfaction level (18). Therefore, it is crucial role of health workers particularly registered nurses (RNs) who providing close monitoring and sharing much of time with patients and their attendance to understand that a sick child's family is crucial to their support and improves clinical judgment and contributes to the development of more user-friendly healthcare systems (19).

Assessing parents' perception of nursing care is important for increasing the quality of pediatric services given the continual burden of illnesses affecting children under five and the importance of family-centered care. Therefore, this study aims to assess parents' perception of nursing care and parental satisfaction in the pediatric department.

Problem Statement

Pediatric ward of District Headquarters Hospital Mirpurkhas has a high incidence of pediatric admissions for children under the age of five due to various disorders. During hospitalization, parents experience fear and hesitation, making nursing support essential for improving their coping and satisfaction. This support includes effective communication, emotional comfort, and involvement in care. However, the extent and quality of nursing support perceived by parents are currently limited, reducing the ability of healthcare providers to meet families' needs. Thus, gathering parents' views on nursing assistance is vital for enhancing family-centered pediatric care and health outcomes.

The Aim of the study

The aim of the study was to assess parents' perceptions of nursing care provided to children under the age of five years admitted in the pediatric department of the District Headquarters Hospital Mirpurkhas, Sindh.

Objectives of the study

- To determine attitudes of nurses' communication and information sharing with parents of admitted children to the pediatric department of District Headquarters Hospital Mirpurkhas. Sindh.
- To identify parents' attitudes towards emotional, appraisal and instrumental support provided by nurses and in the pediatric ward of District Headquarters Hospital Mirpurkhas, Sindh.

Research Question

- What is parents' perception regarding nursing support provided in the Pediatric Department of District Headquarters Hospital Mirpurkhas, Sindh?

Significance of the study

This study examines parents' perceptions of nursing care provided to children under five years of age admitted in the Pediatric Department of the District Headquarters Hospital Mirpurkhas, Sindh, a secondary-level, healthcare facility operating with limited resources. The study provides constructive perceptions into the strengths and gaps in nursing care, specifically in communication, emotional support, and family engagement as perceived by the parents. The findings will inform nursing practice by supporting the development of more effective, patient- and family-centered care approaches. This study contributes to the limited body of evidence on pediatric nursing care in resource-constrained, secondary-level hospitals, thereby contributing to practical implications for increasing the quality of pediatric nursing services in parallel healthcare settings.

Operational Definition

The **parents' perceptions of nursing support** were assessed using a structured questionnaire organized into four domains. Each domain consisted of items measured on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). A total of twenty items were administered to parents at pediatric department of District Headquarters Hospital

Mirpurkhas, Sindh to broadly assess their perceptions on the support provided by nursing staff during their child's hospitalization. Higher scores indicated more positive perceptions of nursing care and support.

Nursing Support refers to the all-encompassing support that nurses give to parents whose children were admitted in the pediatric department of at District Headquarters Hospital Mirpurkhas, Sindh. This support was assessed by evaluating four major domains and calculating mean scores based on established cut-off values. Nursing support is defined as the comprehensive assistance provided by nurses to parents of hospitalized children. In this study, nursing support was assessed across four major domains, with mean scores calculated to determine overall perception. The scoring system used a five-point Likert scale, with interpretation based on established cut-off values: 1.00-1.80 = very poor perception, 1.81-2.60 = poor perception, 2.61-3.40 = moderate perception, 3.41-4.20 = good perception, and 4.21-5.00 = very good perception. Higher scores reflect more positive parental perceptions of nursing support.

Parents refer to the mother, father, or legal guardian of a child under five years of age admitted during the study period in the pediatric department of District Headquarters Hospital Mirpurkhas, Sindh.

METHODOLOGY

Study design

A descriptive cross-sectional design was used in this study to assess parents' perceptions of nursing support for their children admitted to the pediatric ward of District Headquarters Hospital Mirpurkhas. This design allowed for the collection of data at a single point in time to obtain parental perceptions of nursing care during hospitalization.

Study setting

The study was carried out in the Pediatric Department of District Headquarters Hospital Mirpurkhas, Sindh, a secondary level healthcare facility that treats children of all ages both inpatient and outpatient.

Study population

Parents (mother or father) of the admitted children under the age of five.

Sample technique and sample size

A non-probability convenience sampling technique was used. The sample size was calculated using Cochran's formula with finite population correction, assuming a 95% confidence level, and a margin of error of 5%. After applying the finite population correction for the population of 197, the required sample size was 130.

Inclusion criteria

- Parents of children treated as inpatients between November 2025 to January 2026.
- Aged 18 years or above.
- Present in the hospital when the data was being collected.

Exclusion criteria

- Parents whose child spend less than 24 hours in the hospital.
- During data collection, parents were unable to finish the questionnaire or interview.
- To prevent professional prejudice, parents who work in the medical field are not included.

Data collection tool

Data were gathered by using structured questionnaire based on the Nurse-Parent Support Tool (NPST) (20). It has two sections: Section A, focused on socio-demographic information of parents (age, gender, education level, relationship to child), while Section B, assessed perceptions of nursing support across four domains: 1. Information and communication support, 2. Emotional support, 3. Appraisal support, and 4. Instrumental support. Participants' responses were measured on a 5-point Likert scale from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree".

The NPST is a validated and reliable instrument that has been widely used in pediatric and family-centered care research. Previous studies have reported high internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients ranging from 0.88 to 0.96 for the total scale and acceptable reliability across all subscales. The tool also demonstrates strong content and construct validity, as it comprehensively measures key

dimensions of perceived nursing support from the parent's perspective.

For this study, the questionnaire was translated into the local language following a standard forward-backward translation procedure. Initially, the original English version was translated into the local language by a bilingual expert. The translated version was then back-translated into English by an independent translator to ensure conceptual equivalence and accuracy. Any discrepancies were reviewed and resolved by a panel of experts in nursing and research methodology. A pilot test was conducted to assess clarity and cultural appropriateness of the items, and minor modifications were made accordingly. The translated version demonstrated satisfactory reliability in the current study.

Data collection procedure

Following approval from the hospital administration and the institutional ethics committee, eligible parents were approached in the pediatric department by authors, Kinza and Vineeta, with the assistance of the senior nurse (in-charge). The purpose of the study was explained to participants in the local language, and written informed consent was obtained prior to enrollment. Questionnaires were administered and collected on the same day. Participants were assured

of confidentiality, anonymity, and voluntary participation, and were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences.

Data analysis

Data was coded and analyzed using SPSS version 27. Descriptive statistical methods were used. Frequencies, percentages, mean scores and standard deviations assessed parents' perceptions of nursing support. The findings were presented in tables and graphical displays to enhance clarity and interpretation.

Ethical consideration

The approval from the Ethical Review Committee and the permission from the District Headquarters Hospital Mirpurkhas were obtained. The study was voluntary, and each participant's informed consent was recorded. All information gathered was kept confidential, anonymous, and used only for research purposes.

RESULTS

The most respondents were female, making up 76.2% of the participants, while males accounted for 23.8% (Figure 1). This skew may be attributed to the common practice of mothers accompanying their children during hospitalization.

Figure 1: Distribution of Parents According to Gender:

Table 1. Socio-demographic data of the respondents

Demographic Features	Characteristics	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (in years)	18-25Y	48	36.9
	26-35Y	64	49.2
	36-40Y	14	10.8
	40+Y	4	3.1
Education	Uneducated	41	31.5
	Primary	46	35.4
	Secondary	25	19.2
	Higher Education	18	13.8
Marital Status	Married	109	83.8
	Divorced/Widows	21	16.4
Socioeconomic Status (Income per Month)	Less than PKR 30,000	84	64.6
	PKR 30,000-60, 000	38	29.2
	Above PKR 60,000	8	6.2

Residency	Rural	55	41.5
	Urban	75	57.7
Occupation	Housewife	29	22.3
	Private Job	23	17.7
	Government Job	33	25.4
	Self-employed	45	34.6
Duration of Hospital Stay	1-3 days	71	54.6
	4-7 days	49	37.7
	More than 7 days	10	6.9
Total		130	100

The largest group of participants fell within the age range of 26–35 years (49.2%), followed by those aged 18–25 years (36.9%). Concerning education, most respondents had completed primary education (35.4%), while 31.5% were uneducated. Most respondents were married (83.8%). In terms of socioeconomic status, a significant number belonged to the low-income category, earning less than PKR 30,000 monthly (64.6%). More than half of the respondents lived in urban settings (57.7%). Concerning their occupation, the largest percentage was self-employed at (34.6%), followed by (25.3%) who were government employees. In relation to the length of hospital stay, most children were admitted for a period of 1–3 days (54.6%). The details are given in above Table 1.

Domain Wise Nursing Support

1. Information Giving and Communication Support

The parents reported favorable perceptions of nurses' information giving and communication support. High levels of agreement were noted for nurses answering questions clearly (89.2% agree/strongly agree) and informing parents about changes in the child's condition (93.8%). Most parents also agreed that nurses involved them in decision-making (74.6%) and allowed them to choose whether to remain during procedures (83.1%). Moderate agreement was observed for explanations related to childcare (60.8%) and understanding of the child's behavior (60.0%). Lower levels of agreement were reported for nurses explaining procedures and care (51.5%) and teaching parents how to comfort their child during or after procedures (50.8%), with a relatively higher proportion of undecided responses. The lowest agreement was noted for identifying the names and roles of staff caring for the child (24.6%), indicating a gap in role clarification and staff identification (Table 2).

Table 2. Information giving and communication support

Statement(s)	Agree	Strongly agreed	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Undecided
Nurses involved me in decision-making about my child's care.	(n=69) 53.1%	(n=28) 21.5%	(n=10) 7.7%	(n=3) 2.3%	(n=12) 9.2%
Nurses informed me about changes in my child's condition.	(n=68) 52.3%	(n=54) 41.5%	(n=1) 0.8%	(n=0) 0.00%	(n=7) 5.4%
Nurses explained how to care for my child.	(n=49) 37.7%	(n=30) 23.1%	(n=23) 17.7%	(n=10) 7.7%	(n=18) 13.8%

Nurses helped me understand my child's behavior and reactions.	(n=50) 38.5%	(n=28) 21.5%	(n=20) 15.4%	(n=6) 4.6%	(n=26) 20.0%
Nurses allowed me to choose whether to stay during medical procedures.	(n=59) 45.4%	(n=49) 37.7%	(n=12) 9.2%	(n=0) 0.00%	(n=10) 7.7%
Nurses answered my questions clearly and satisfactorily.	(n=45) 34.6%	(n=71) 54.6%	(n=1) 0.8%	(n=2) 1.5%	(n=11) 8.5%
Nurses explained the procedures and care provided to my child.	(n=54) 41.5%	(n=13) 10.0%	(n=13) 10.0%	(n=7) 5.4%	(n=43) 33.1%
Nurses taught me how to comfort my child during and after procedures.	(n=56) 43.1%	(n=10) 7.7%	(n=18) 13.8%	(n=4) 3.1%	(n=42) 32.3%
Nurses helped me identify the names and roles of staff caring for my child.	(n=25) 19.2%	(n=7) 5.4%	(n=34) 26.2%	(n=37) 28.5%	(n=27) 20.8%

2. Emotional Support

Most parents reported positive perceptions of emotional support, with 83.1% agreeing or strongly agreeing that nurses showed concern for their well-

being encouraged expression of feelings and concerns. Disagreement and undecided responses were minimal (Table 3).

Table 3. Emotional Support

Emotionally support	Agreed	Strongly agreed	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Undecided
Nurses showed concern about my well-being and worries.	(n=56) 43.1%	(n=52) 40.0%	(n=16) 12.3%	(n=2) 1.5%	(n=4) 3.1%
Nurses encouraged me to express my feelings and concerns.	(n=46) 35.4%	(n=62) 47.7%	(n=9) 6.9%	(n=1) 0.8%	(n=12) 9.2%

3. Appraisal Support

The findings show that the parents reported very high satisfaction with nurses' responsiveness, with 97.7% agreeing with or strongly agreeing that nurses responded promptly to their child's needs. Moderate agreement was observed for nurses' sensitivity to the

child's individual needs (77.7%). However, lower levels of agreement were noted regarding nurses showing warmth and care (23.8%) and encouraging parents to ask questions (52.3%), with relatively higher proportions of disagreement and undecided responses (Table 4).

Table 4: Appraisal support

Appraisal support	Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Undecided
Nurses responded promptly to my child's needs.	(n=43) 33.1%	(n=84) 64.6%	(n=1) 0.8%	(n=1) 0.8%	(n=1) 0.8%
Nurses showed warmth and care toward my child.	(n=18) 13.8%	(n=13) 10.0%	(n=37) 28.5%	(n=18) 13.8%	(n=44) 33.8%
Nurses were sensitive to my child's individual need.	(n=56) 43.1%	(n=45) 34.6%	(n=9) 6.9%	(n=1) 0.8%	(n=190) 14.6%
Nurses encouraged me to ask questions about my child's care.	(n=53) 40.8%	(n=15) 11.5%	(n=21) 16.2%	(n=7) 5.4%	(n=34) 26.2%

4. Instrumental Support

The parents reported very high agreement that nurses provided quality care to their children (95.4%). Most parents also agreed that nurses involved them in their child's care (78.4%) and expressed optimism about the child's condition

(67.7%). In contrast, lower agreement was observed for nurses acknowledging parental efforts (30.7%) and making parents feel valued (10.0%), with higher levels of disagreement and undecided responses in these areas (Table 5).

Table 5: Instrumental support

Instrumental support	Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Undecided
Nurses provided quality care to my child.	(n=26) 20.0%	(n=98) 75.4%	(n=3) 2.3%	(n=0) 0.00%	(n=3) 2.3%
Nurses involved me in my child's care whenever possible.	(n=77) 59.2%	(n=25) 19.2%	(n=5) 3.8%	(n=1) 0.8%	(n=22) 16.9%
Nurses expressed optimism about my child's condition.	(n=68) 52.3%	(n=20) 15.4%	(n=4) 3.1%	(n=4) 3.1%	(n=34) 26.2%
Nurses acknowledged my efforts in caring for my child.	(n=35) 26.9%	(n=5) 3.8%	(n=22) 16.9%	(n=21) 16.2%	(n=47) 36.2%
Nurses made me feel valued as a parent.	(n=12) 9.2%	(n=1) 0.8%	(n=32) 24.6%	(n=37) 28.5%	(n=48) 36.9%

Table 6. Domain-Wise Mean Scores of Parents' Perception of Nursing Support

Mean scores were interpreted using predetermined cut-off values: 1.00–1.80 (very poor), 1.81–2.60 (poor), 2.61–3.40 (moderate), 3.41–4.20 (good), and

4.21–5.00 (very good) (21). The findings in Table 6 show that parents had an overall good perception of nursing support, with a mean score of 3.79 ± 0.40 . Among the domains, emotional support received the highest mean score (4.15 ± 0.89), indicating strong

positive perceptions of nurses' emotional care. Overall, parents perceived nursing support in the

pediatric department positively, with emotional support rated most favorably.

Table 6. Domain Wise Mean Scores of Parents' Perception of Nursing Support (n = 130).

Domain	Mean X	±SD	Interpretation
Information Giving & Communication Support	3.72	0.52	Good
Emotional Support	4.15	0.89	Good
Appraisal Support	3.75	0.47	Good
Informational Support	3.53	0.57	Good
Overall Nursing Support	3.79	0.40	Good

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study showed that parents of children under five admitted to the pediatric department at District Headquarters Hospital Mirpurkhas, Sindh, generally perceived overall good level of nursing support. This indicates that nursing staff played a positive role in supporting parents during their child's hospitalization, particularly in emotional care and communication. These findings emphasize the role of nurse support in lowering parental stress and promoting coping during pediatric hospitalization, as highlighted in family-centered care approaches (22). This study revealed that emotional support received the highest score of 4.15 (SD = 0.89) in parents' perceptions of nurse assistance. These results are in contrast with previous findings, which indicated that emotional support scored lowest among parents' perceptions, while information and communication support were rated the highest (5). This highlights the importance of emotional care in pediatric nursing, as it helps reduce psychological distress and parental anxiety during hospitalization(23, 24).

According to the findings of this study, most parents felt that nurses were adequately informed and communicated with them about their child's health, care, and procedures. Parents reported being informed about changes in their child's condition and being given the opportunity to participate in decision-making, which reflects positive communication skills. This finding aligns with previous research that indicates effective communication and parental involvement in care decisions enhance parents' trust in nurses and overall satisfaction with the care provided (25). Effective communication has also been identified as a core component of family-centered care in pediatric settings (26). In terms of appraisal support

were also perceived as good (mean = 3.75 ± 0.47). Many parents stated that nurses were attentive and responsive to their child's needs and encouraged them to ask questions. Previous study reported similar results, emphasizing that parental support and responsiveness increase patient satisfaction with care and build trust in healthcare providers (27). This shows a supportive care setting where parents feel respected and actively participate in providing care. Instrumental support was also perceived as good mean = 3.53 ± 0.57), with most parents strongly agreed that nurses provided good care for their children and involved them in care whenever possible. However, a significant percentage of parents expressed doubt or dissatisfaction about the degree to which nurses recognized their role and gave them a sense of worth as caregivers. This suggests that while task-oriented nursing care is successful, there is still opportunity for improvement in terms of emotional validation and parental acknowledgment. Previous research has repeatedly shown that meaningful parental involvement improves care outcomes and satisfaction (28-30).

Overall, the results of this investigation are consistent with national and worldwide research showing moderate to good levels of parental satisfaction with nursing care in pediatric settings, previous study reported similar results (22). Despite gaps in communication, parental empowerment and support received positive ratings, in line with research from Pakistan and other developing countries. Differences in hospital environments, nurse-to-patient ratios, and cultural expectations regarding parental involvement may account for the discrepancies between this study and previous research. The findings, which align with those of earlier studies, suggest that to enhance the quality of pediatric healthcare services, it is essential

to strengthen family-centered nursing practices, particularly in non-tertiary care hospital settings(31).

CONCLUSION

The study found that parents of children under five at the pediatric department of District Headquarters Hospital Mirpurkhas, Sindh, generally viewed nursing support positively and good, especially in emotional care, which was rated highest. While information sharing and communication were also favored, there were gaps in recognizing parental efforts and clarifying staff roles. Strengthening family-centered nursing practices is essential to improve parental satisfaction, reduce stress, and enhance pediatric healthcare quality.

LIMITATIONS

This study faced several limitations. Firstly, it was conducted in a single pediatric department at a non-tertiary care hospital, potentially limiting the generalizability of the findings to more specialized settings. Secondly, the cross-sectional design didn't allow for assessing changes in parents' perceptions over time. Also, the study focused only on parents of children under five, making findings less applicable to those with older children. Lastly, the small sample size due to time and financial constraints may affect the representativeness of the results

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Nurse parent communication should be strengthened, particularly regarding explanation of procedures, staff roles, and guidance on child comfort.
- Nurses should actively acknowledge parents' caregiving efforts and involve them as partners in care to enhance parental satisfaction.
- Regular in-service training for nurses on communication skills, emotional support, and family-centered care is recommended.
- Future studies should employ multi-center designs with larger samples to improve generalizability of findings

IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICE

Efficient nursing support for parents of hospitalized children plays a significant role in lowering caregiver stress and apprehension. Nursing support also builds

trust among healthcare professionals and augments inclusive satisfaction with hospital services. These consequences have direct implications for pediatric care because emotionally supported and informed caregivers can contribute to child's care and decision-making in better ways. Hence, pediatric nursing practice should spotlight structured nurse-parent communication, emotional support, and family-centered care approaches to improve both parental experiences and child health outcomes.

CREDIT AUTHORSHIP CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT

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Data collection. Vineeta & Kinza
Review, methodology & editing: Lachman Das Malhi & Irfan Ali
All authors read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST DISCLOSURE

The authors declare they have no conflicts of interest.

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REFERENCES

1. Ansariniaki M, Alaei S, Khoshdast Kakhki M, Mirmohammadkhani M. Caring behavior: perspectives from nurses and parents of hospitalized children. *BMC pediatrics*. 2025;25(1):1-8.
2. Lean RE, Rogers CE, Paul RA, Gerstein ED. NICU hospitalization: long-term implications on parenting and child behaviors. *Current treatment options in pediatrics*. 2018;4(1):49-69.

3. Rifai SI, Mukaromah RS, Nugraha D, Fuadah NT. Nurses' Caring Behavior, Parental Anxiety and Satisfaction in Pediatric Inpatient War. *Indonesian J Global Health Res.* 2024;6(1):213-22.
4. Boztepe H, Kerimoğlu Yıldız G, Çınar Özbay S, Ay A. Determination of factors affecting the status of hospitalized child's parent for receiving family-centered care. *Acıbadem Üniversitesi Sağlık Bilimleri Dergisi.* 2019;10(4):748-55.
5. Oztas G, Akca SO. Levels of nursing support and satisfaction of parents with children having pediatric inpatient care. *Journal of Pediatric Nursing.* 2024;77:e24-e30.
6. Rehman F-U, Yousufzai AUR, Bibi A, Herbert A, Jawed Y, Hameed U, et al. Parental Satisfaction with Health Care During Child Hospitalization at Tertiary Care Hospital Karachi: Parental Satisfaction with Health Care During Child Hospitalization. *Pakistan Journal of Health Sciences.* 2024:45-9.
7. Abuqamar M, Arabiat DH, Holmes S. Parents' perceived satisfaction of care, communication and environment of the pediatric intensive care units at a tertiary children's hospital. *Journal of pediatric nursing.* 2016;31(3):e177-e84.
8. Kibret H, Tadesse B, Debella A, Degefa M, Regassa LD. The Association of nurses caring behavior with the level of patient satisfaction, Harari region, Eastern Ethiopia. *Nursing: Research and Reviews.* 2022:47-56.
9. Prasannan S, Thomas D. A Study to Determine the Level of Satisfaction of Parents with the Nursing Care for Children Admitted in Paediatric Oncology Ward and Seek its Association with Selected Factors in Selected government Hospitals of Delhi. *Int J Heal Sci Res Nurs Off [Internet].* 2018;8(10):150.
10. Sinha B, Chaudhary R, Karn BK, Yadav U, Shah S. Nurse-Parent Communication in Pediatric Units of B. P Koirala Institute of Health Sciences, Dharan, Nepal: A Parent's Perspective Study.
11. Villalona S, Boxtha C, Webb WA, Cervantes C, Wilson JW. "If at least the patient could not be forgotten about": communication in the emergency department as a predictor of patient satisfaction. *Journal of patient experience.* 2020;7(6):1015-21.
12. Chandio IA, Channar HB, Abbas Z, Imdad S. FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH NEONATAL ADMISSION TO NEONATAL INTENSIVE CARE UNIT AND THEIR OUTCOME AT LIAQUAT UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL, HYDERABAD.
13. Alzawad Z, Lewis FM, Kantrowitz-Gordon I, Howells AJ. A qualitative study of parents' experiences in the pediatric intensive care unit: riding a roller coaster. *Journal of pediatric nursing.* 2020;51:8-14.
14. Alzawad Z, Lewis FM, Ngo L, Thomas K. Exploratory model of parental stress during children's hospitalisation in a paediatric intensive care unit. *Intensive and Critical Care Nursing.* 2021;67:103109.
15. WHO. Child mortality (under 5 years) 2020. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/child-mortality-under-5-years>.
16. Talpur MA, Channar HB, Junejo Z, Chandio IA, ul Haque M, Shahok S. FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH MALNUTRITION UNDER FIVE YEARS CHILDREN AT LIAQUAT UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL, HYDERABAD. *cognitive development.* 2025;3(10).
17. Tharwani ZH, Bilal W, Khan HA, Kumar P, Butt MS, Hamdana AH, et al. Infant & child mortality in Pakistan and its determinants: a review. *INQUIRY: The Journal of Health Care Organization, Provision, and Financing.* 2023;60:00469580231167024.
18. Ojewale LY, Akingbohungebe O, Akinokun RT, Akingbade O. Caregivers' perception of the quality of nursing care in child health care services of the University College Hospital, Nigeria. *Journal of Pediatric Nursing.* 2022;66:120-4.

19. Johnson JO. Implementation of family centered care for neonates admitted in a special care baby unit in Sierra Leone. *Pediatric Health, Medicine and Therapeutics*. 2024;189-99.
20. Kerthu HS, Maano NE. Perception of parents on nursing support rendered to parents with neonates admitted to neonatal intensive care unit in a state hospital in Windhoek, Namibia. *Clinical Nursing Studies [Internet]*. 2019;22-9.
21. Sözen E, Güven U. The Effect of Online Assessments on Students' Attitudes towards Undergraduate-Level Geography Courses. *International Education Studies*. 2019;12(10):1-8.
22. Foster M, Whitehead L, Arabiat D, Frost L. Parents' and staff perceptions of parental needs during a child's hospital admission: An Australian study. *Journal of Pediatric Nursing*. 2018;43:e2-e9.
23. Konukbay D, Vural M, Yildiz D. Parental stress and nurse-parent support in the neonatal intensive care unit: a cross-sectional study. *BMC nursing*. 2024;23(1):820.
24. Scott G, Dunn LM, Dow B, Kenardy J, De Young AC, Long DA. Interventions to Support Psychological Health Outcomes for Children and Families Experiencing Paediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) Admission: A Scoping Review. *Nursing in Critical Care*. 2025;30(3):e70057.
25. Foldager Jeppesen S, Vilhjálmsón R, Ávik Persson H, Kristensson Hallström I. Parental satisfaction with paediatric care with and without the support of an eHealth device: a quasi-experimental study in Sweden. *BMC Health Services Research*. 2024;24(1):41.
26. Alabdulaziz H, Moss C, Copnell B. Paediatric nurses' perceptions and practices of family-centred care in Saudi hospitals: A mixed methods study. *International journal of nursing studies*. 2017;69:66-77.
27. Palomaa A-K, Hakala M, Pölkki T. Parents' perceptions of their child's pain assessment in hospital care: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of pediatric nursing*. 2023;71:79-87.
28. Loureiro F, Antunes V. Instruments to evaluate hospitalised children parents' satisfaction with nursing care: a scoping review. *BMJ Paediatrics Open*. 2022;6(1):e001568.
29. Bütün A, Özyurt M. Level of Satisfaction of Parents of Children with Nursing Care in the Paediatric Emergency Departments. *Anatolian Journal of Emergency Medicine*. 2025;8(2):82-90.
30. Kato Y, Kawahara T, Endo Y, Yamazaki A. Difficulties in providing nursing care to children with neurodevelopmental disorders admitted to child and adolescent psychiatric units for aggressive behavior. *Japan Journal of Nursing Science*. 2025;22(2):e70001.
31. Terp K, Weis J, Lundqvist P. Parents' views of family-centered care at a pediatric intensive care unit—a qualitative study. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*. 2021;9:725040.